

Correlation Analysis of Emotional Control of Workers, Healthy Nutrition and Labor Experience and Operative Yielding in a Metallic Industry of Tijuana, México

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Abstract – The emotional control is a relevant in the actions of people, because can represents the way of behavior of each person, being important in the elaboration of any type of activity, and especially in the industrial operations of industrial companies in all places of the world. This investigation represents an evaluation of the diverse emotional aspects by workers in a metallic industry, analyzing the nutrition food, labor relation between supervisors and workers of industrial machines and industrial equipments, healthy symptoms of workers of industrial lines with industrial processes and the operative yielding of the people who works in the manufacturing areas of this metallic industry evaluated. To control the emotions of workers was made necessary use the active breaks with motivational pop music in the industrial processes in indoors of the metallic industry, where was made this scientific study, which supported to decrease the stress of workers of the industrial processes. When were controlled the emotions of workers, the operative yielding of this workers was efficient and increased the productivity and quality levels, and with this was presented economic gains in this industry evaluated.

Keywords: Emotional control, metallic industry, stress, healthy symptoms, active breaks.

1. INTRODUCTION

Emotional actions are relevant in the development of any type of functions of all persons in any place of the world, being important in the industrial operations, where are presented in some time diverse type of critical situations, which are depending of the emotions control of workers that elaborate industrial operations in the manufacturing areas of any type of industrial company (Meybeck et al, 2017). In this investigation, was made an analysis of the relation of emotional actions of person of the manufacturing areas, where are presented in a lot times, the labor stress, associated with the healthy nutrition and inexperience actions, which are relevant in the operative yielding of workers of the industrial processes (Caputo et al, 2019). This scientific study was relevant to control these three interesting actions of persons of industrial operations, and obtain the maximum operative yielding of workers of these areas in the metallic industry, which is located in an industrial city as is Tijuana city, where are around 150 industrial companies that manufactures metallic products (AIMT, 2023). The results show that is necessary act about these three relevant factors, to obtain high efficiency in the productivity and quality indices, in this metallic industry evaluated in any type of industria company. Figure 1 shows the three essential aspects to obtain the maximum efficiency of the operative yielding in the industrial operations (Rerkjirattikal et al, 2021; Cheaitou et al, 2019).

Fig -1: Essential factors to an efficient operative yielding of workers in industrial activities

Source: Analysis of the investigation.

1.1 Healthy Nutrition

This is an important aspect in the regulations of metabolic of persons to have an efficient operative yielding of any type of functions that develop in the labor activities or other type of activities. In the actual times, the nutrition factor is not essential in the in the daily life of most people in the world and especially in the Tijuana city (Hochdörffer et al, 2018). This is a part of the personnel discipline of each individual of each population, being relevant in his health actions, where have an effect (positive or negative) in this health and in his operative yielding, especially in the industrial activities, where the majorly of industrial operations are very hard or have labor stress. With good nutrition, persons have good health and efficient operative yielding. This is part of the familiar discipline and customs, and in the scholar activities (Brenda Gabriela Alarcón Sandoval et al, 2024). In figure 2 are presented the principal aspects to have a healthy nutrition and have an efficient operative yielding in industrial operations (Botti et al, 2020).

Fig -2: Main aspects to a good healthy nutrition and efficient operative yielding of workers in industrial activities

Source: Analysis of the investigation.

1.2 Emotional Control

This relevant actions in the behavior of each person, which have impact in emotional actions and also, in the operative yielding of any person in any type of activities, essentially in the industrial operations, where need control the emotions, for the diverse type of critical situations that occurs in the manufacturing processes of the industrial companies in any place of the world (Kuc-Czarnecka et al, 2023). All persons have in any time, one emotional action, and is necessary control it, to have the mind without concerns and free of any information that can affects the thought process, and can make our functions with the maximum efficiency and clarity. Figure 3 illustrates the main aspects to control the emotions of any person (Dul et al, 2012).

Fig -3: Principal factors to the emotional control and efficient operative yielding of workers in industrial activities

Source: Analysis of the investigation.

1.3 Industrial Experience to Maximum Efficiency in Manufacturing Areas

Is an important action in the development of industrial operations, which are depending of the level of experience of each worker or the manufacturing area, including some type of technical and professional knowledges (Battini et al, 2022). This factor is relevant at the moment to reach and meet goals and

objectives of any type of industrial operations. Figure 4 illustrates the principal factors to obtain good industrial experience (Mondejar et al, 2021).

Fig -4: Essential elements to obtain good experience to an efficient operative yielding of workers in industrial activities

Source: Analysis of the investigation.

1.4 Metallic Industry in Tijuana

Is an important industry of the countries that develop this type of industrial operations, being relevant in the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and generating a lot quantity of employments and millions of dollars by the fabrication of diverse metallic products that are utilized to a large extent in a lot daily activities in all places of the world (Wheeler et al, 2013; Finco et al, 2021). In Tijuana city are a lot construction companies and individual persons that use diverse type of metallic products. In table 1 is presented the principal metallic products manufactured in the metallic industry of Tijuana (AIMT, 2023).

Table -1: Essential metallic products manufactured in the metallic industry of Tijuana (2023)

Characteristics	Type of metallic material	Type of Process Flow	Application
Metallic Products			
Metallic Structures for Construction	Steel, Nickel, Zinc	Lineal and U-Line	Construction of Budlings, Bridges and other metallic structures in the daily life
Metallic Hoses for Water, Gas and Electricity Installations	Steel, Nickel, Copper	Lineal and T-Line	Use in pipelines of water, gas or electricity
Manufactured Metallic Products for Home Furnishings	Steel, Nickel, Zinc	Lineal and G-Line	Utilized in home furniture

2. METHODOLOGY

This scientific study is very interesting to specialists of the metallic structures, where are utilized in a lot type of activities of the daily life, being elaborated some activities as are expressed now:

- a) Correlation analysis of healthy symptoms and emotional workers of workers of the manufacturing areas and his operative yielding.

- b) Evaluation of the relation of operative persons and supervisors, being related with his operative yielding.
- c) Analysis of production factors.

3. RESULTS

This investigation was made to determine if the relevant aspects mentioned above (healthy nutrition, emotional control and industrial experience), were any type of impact and know the grade of this impact.

3.1 Evaluation of Healthy Symptoms, Emotional Control and Industrial Experience

In this section was made an analysis to determine the relation between the health, emotional control and experience of workers that indicated the form the way in which it can be known if a worker in the manufacturing area of the evaluated company can have an optimal operative yielding. This was very important to delimit functions to each worker of the industrial processes of this metalworking industry, where this relevant scientific study was carried out, and thereby obtain maximum efficiency in productivity and quality indices. This is shown in figure 5, which illustrates in the period of the research study (2023), how cases of workers in the manufacturing area were presented, who present symptoms of nutritional health, emotional control and the action of work experience. In this figure it is observed that for the nutrition factor in health, in this scientific study, serious cases were presented in 85 workers. It is then presented for the aspect of emotional control with 95 workers with complex situations and 105 industrial process workers with work experience, who suffered from the two factors mentioned in this section. This figure shows also, the relation of the three relevant factors mentioned above, but other aspect of interest, was the inexperience that generated the presence of healthy nutrition and emotional control, when these workers were working in his operations. These evaluations were related with the operative yielding of workers and also, with the productivity and quality levels.

Fig -5: Evaluation of healthy nutrition, emotional control and industrial experience of works (2023)

3.2 Analysis of Labor Relation in the Metallic Industry Evaluated

In this part of the investigation were evaluated some relevant aspects that can have impact in the operative yielding of the workers of the manufacturing area of the metallic industry where was made this important scientific study. This evaluation was interesting because in base of the relation of workers of manufacturing areas and supervisor and including the managers, was presented an efficient or inefficient operative yielding, and with this the productivity and quality indices, originating the necessary improvements to maintain a good relation and with this, an efficient operative yielding. This caused economical gains and economical bonus to workers. This is expressed in table 2 with the percentages levels of each relevant factor evaluated. The improvements were necessary to repeat in all cases of this analysis.

Table -2: Relevant factors of workers of manufacturing areas and operative yielding (2023)

Factors Workers	Level of Labor Relation	Operative Yielding	Improvement Actions
1	76	78	Improve the relation and recognize the labor of workers from supervisors and managers and generates capacitation courses.
2	84	83	Improve the relation and recognize the labor of workers from supervisors and managers and generates capacitation courses.
3	80	85	Improve the relation and recognize the labor of workers from supervisors and managers and generates capacitation courses.
4	86	83	Improve the relation and recognize the labor of workers from supervisors and managers and generates capacitation courses.
5	79	80	Improve the relation and recognize the labor of workers from supervisors and managers and generates capacitation courses.
6	75	77	Improve the relation and recognize the labor of workers from supervisors and managers and generates capacitation courses.
7	80	79	Improve the relation and recognize the labor of workers from supervisors and managers and generates capacitation courses.
8	87	86	Improve the relation and recognize the labor of workers from supervisors and managers
9	88	88	Improve the relation and recognize the labor of workers from supervisors and managers and generates capacitation courses.
10	92	90	Improve the relation and recognize the labor of workers from supervisors and managers and generates capacitation courses.

3.3 Evaluation of Productivity and Quality Indices

Once the analysis of the previous sections was carried out, the productivity and quality levels were analyzed, without having developed any type of improvement (as the industrial process was currently in the evaluated manufacturing areas) and with the improvements generated by this scientific study, and the results are illustrated in table 3. To improve the operative yielding of workers were made courses of healthy nutrition, emotional control and manufacturing activities to obtain industrial experience very fast and good, and increase every time the productivity and quality, as is showed in table 3 that was increased these relevant factors, conforms was advancing this investigation. The improvements were necessary to repeat in all cases of this analysis.

Table -3: Evaluation of productivity and quality levels in the metallic industry of Tijuana (2023)

Production Factors	Productivity, %	Quality, %	Improvement Actions
Months			
1	68	59	Control of nutritive food, emotions and capacitation courses of healthy nutrition, emotional control and manufacturing activities.
2	72	63	Control of nutritive food, emotions and capacitation courses of healthy nutrition, emotional control and manufacturing activities.
3	75	66	Control of nutritive food, emotions and capacitation courses of healthy nutrition, emotional control and manufacturing activities.
4	77	68	Control of nutritive food, emotions and capacitation courses of healthy nutrition, emotional control and manufacturing activities.
5	79	69	Control of nutritive food, emotions and capacitation courses of healthy nutrition, emotional control and manufacturing activities.
6	78	72	Control of nutritive food, emotions and capacitation courses of healthy nutrition, emotional control and manufacturing activities.
7	82	75	Control of nutritive food, emotions and capacitation courses of healthy nutrition, emotional control and manufacturing activities.
8	80	77	Control of nutritive food, emotions and capacitation courses of healthy nutrition, emotional control and manufacturing activities.
9	83	85	Control of nutritive food, emotions and capacitation courses of healthy nutrition, emotional control and manufacturing activities.

10	85	83	Control of nutritive food, emotions and capacitation courses of healthy nutrition, emotional control and manufacturing activities.
11	87	80	Control of nutritive food, emotions and capacitation courses of healthy nutrition, emotional control and manufacturing activities.
12	85	84	Control of nutritive food, emotions and capacitation courses of healthy nutrition, emotional control and manufacturing activities.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This scientific study supports to improve some relevant factors as the healthy nutrition, emotional control and industrial experience of workers of the manufacture areas evaluated, obtaining efficient results after made this investigation and supports to care the health of workers as physical and mental health. This analysis was very important, because workers learn to work with labor stress and improve his operative yielding and with this have a positive impact in the increase of productivity and quality indices. This investigation was made in a industrial company that fabricates metallic products, but other industrial companies, which manufactures others types of products to customers, want to make a similar scientific study, to improve its productivity and quality levels.

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